

Product user guide for the high-resolution unstructured wave hindcast along the Australian coast

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1 Wave parameters

The high-resolution unstructured wave hindcast along the Australian coast was conducted using the spectral wave model WAVEWATCH III, incorporating the observation-based source term package ST6 and a national-scale unstructured mesh with spatial resolutions ranging from 1 to 15 km. In the complex Great Barrier Reef region, the mesh was further refined to a 1 km resolution, and a subgrid-scale reef parameterization was implemented to account for wave attenuation and improve model accuracy. The final mesh consists of 185,285 nodes and 348,631 elements. For more detailed information, please refer to the main text of this study.

1.1 Gridded output (Unst1km_Grd)

The field wave parameters are stored on a national unstructured triangular grid with a temporal resolution of 3 hours. Table 1 summarises all the wave parameters that are available in the hindcast.

Table 1: Wave parameters available in the wave hindcast

File name	Definition
<i>1) Forcing fields</i>	
wnd	wind speed u_{10}, v_{10} (m s^{-1})
cur	tidal current velocity $ucur, vcur$ (m s^{-1})
wlv	water levels wlv (m)

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File name	Definition
<i>2) Standard mean wave parameters</i>	
hs	significant wave height H_s (m)
lm	mean wave length L_m (m)
t02	wave period $T_{0,2}$ (s)
t0m1	wave period $T_{0,-1}$ (s)
t01	wave period $T_{0,1}$ (s)
fp	peak frequency f_p (Hz)
dir	mean wave direction θ_m ($^\circ$)
spr	directional spreading σ_θ ($^\circ$)
dp	peak direction θ_p ($^\circ$)
<i>4) Spectral partition parameters for wind sea and up to 3 swell systems</i>	
“?” below represents the identifier number for a given partition, where ? = 0, 1, 2, 3 denote wind sea, primary swell, secondary swell, and tertiary swell, respectively.	
phs?	significant wave height H_s (m)
ptp?	peak wave period T_p (s)
plp?	peak wave length L_p (m)
pdir?	mean direction θ_m ($^\circ$)
pspr?	directional spreading σ_θ ($^\circ$)
pws?	wind sea fraction of the given partition W (-)
pdp?	peak direction θ_p ($^\circ$)
pqp?	Goda peakedness parameter of partition Q_p (-)
ppe?	JONSWAP peak enhancement factor of partition γ (-)
ptm10c?	wave energy period T_E (i.e., $T_{0,-1}$) (s)
pt01c?	wave period $T_{0,1}$ (s)
pt02c?	wave period $T_{0,2}$ (s)
tws	wind sea fraction of the entire spectrum (-)
<i>5) Atmosphere-waves layer</i>	
cge	energy flux $C_g E$ (kW m^{-1})
<i>6) Wave-Ocean layer</i>	
tus	Stokes volume transport ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)
uss	surface Stokes drift (m s^{-1})
<i>8) Spectrum parameters</i>	
mss	(down-wave & cross-wave) mean square slope $\langle s^2 \rangle$ (-)
msd	mean square slope direction ($^\circ$)
msc	Phillips tail constant (spectral tail level) (-)
mcd	tail slope direction ($^\circ$)

1.2 Point output (Unst1km_Pnt)

Two-dimensional wave spectra are archived at selected buoy locations and during specific time periods to match the observational records provided by the Australian Ocean Data Network (AODN). Some buoys may change their locations many times during their lifetime because of redeployment. Therefore, one should check the data files (i.e., `ww3_yyyymm_spec.nc`) to get the specific locations and duration of each buoy. Additionally, the hindcast provides wave spectral data at 2,001 spatial points across the model domain, covering the entire simulation period (from 1979). The spatial resolution is $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$, with further refinement to $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ in key areas such as Sydney and Melbourne (see Fig. 1). All point outputs are provided with a temporal resolution of 1 hour.

Figure 1: Point output locations on the regular $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ grid, with red polygons highlighting key regions where the resolution is refined to $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$.

2 Access to the hindcast (Data Mover)

The wave hindcast product is stored at the [Mediaflux](#) platform, maintained by the [Research Computing Services \(RCS\)](#) at the University of Melbourne. The corresponding project is proj_4320_ww3_st6_unstructured_australia_hindcast-1128.4.1180.

When you click on the specific shareable link (Section 2.1), the [Data Mover](#) client will launch automatically if it is already installed; otherwise, your web browser will prompt you to download the installer. Once launched, the Data Mover presents a simple GUI (Fig. 2) for downloading data.

Figure 2: Data Mover GUI

Figure 3: File Download List within the Data Mover Client

Alternatively, you can [install the Data Mover client manually](#). After launching it, click the “Add new” button and paste the shareable link to begin the download process.

Once you have accessed the download list (Fig. 3), refer to Section 1 for guidance on selecting data for specific time periods as needed.

2.1 Shareable Link for Data Download

Unst1km_Grd :

```
https://mediaflux.researchsoftware.unimelb.edu.au/mflux/data/mover/index.html?token=kg48rxcqq76v15kvwvsfj2iqkvmijugyydjrqr2jq8gseyh4ojrt1nw0rg3dq2k701231v5klxose7z8nrm7eccvx47plvypfhpw0141zwp8sno8fmnc1jwlo36uaj5os87by9ddzxgoxgwzguflkbw4sujby0dot21kc40kzs1zv7q5fbaq45jf35lin1nmu6akj0o3oamskdrvcvch4z85kqxb6xeno7594a
```

Unst1km_Pnt :

```
https://mediaflux.researchsoftware.unimelb.edu.au/mflux/data/mover/index.html?token=kg48rxcqq76v15kvwvsfj2iqkvmijugyydjrqr2jq8gseyh4ojrt1nw0rg3dq2k701231v5klxose7z8nrm7eccvx47plvyr8nflaasponu957fr6plibpb3b07hm60hx4ckcweezw7ngr2tv8grwro0891h2p2u85fkwe1tu2k19xx4yep3loy5oa0cvdr9rnz3o826fhi0jf0luu4a2lvni7y2ixh1189375
```

3 Feedback and Support

If you find anything unclear or any problems in the dataset, please don't hesitate to contact us. For specific data requests, feel free to reach out as well.

If you encounter any issues installing or using the Data Mover, please refer to [Data Mover Reference](#).